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Economic Dispatch of Hydrothermal System

Teodora D. Denić¹ and Lidija M. Korunović²

Abstract – This paper addresses the problem of economic dispatch of hydrothermal system, i.e. hydrothermal coordination (HTC) problem. The paper proposes the mathematical model for HTC and applies it to solve a specific optimization problem, utilizing a publicly available software package, and discusses the main results and the efficiency of applied software.

Keywords – Economic dispatch, Hydrothermal coordination, Mathematical model, Optimization problem, Program package.

I. INTRODUCTION

The economic dispatch (ED) is an important segment of short-term operation planning in electric power systems. Its main goal is to coordinate the operation of power plants in the considered system to minimize their operating costs, while safe and high-quality operation of the system are ensured. This coordination is carried out in both day-ahead scheduling, and real-time operation.

In hydrothermal systems, where electric energy is produced in hydro and thermal power plants (HPPs and TPPs), specific techno-economic analyses are necessary to determine the optimal, economic coordination of the engaged units. Opposite to TPPs, which are characterized by high fuel costs of electricity production, no changes in operating costs of hydropower units are attributed to water, as the primary energy source [1]. That is the fundamental economic difference between the operation of HPPs and TPPs, which influences on their application in electric power systems. Thus, it can be simply stated that the operation of mentioned power plants should be coordinated in such a way that the maximum possible amount of energy is obtained from the available water potential in HPPs, while energy production in TPPs is carried out with the lowest possible operating costs. However, the parameters that determine energy production in these systems are numerous [2].

Due to the high dimensionality, nonlinearity and numerous constraints, the ED of hydrothermal systems represents a complex optimization problem. Variety of approaches to this problem can be found in numerous references, which differ in terms of proposed models and solution methods. The classic ED of hydrothermal systems is detailed in [1]-[3]. In addition, possible aspects of the extending HTC model can be found in [4], and include: security constraints; ramp-rate limits of thermal units; valve-point loading effects of thermal generation; prohibited operating zones of generation units;

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environmental concerns; incorporation of renewable energy sources; etc.

Optimization methods used to solve HTC problem can be classified into two main groups: deterministic (classical, exact) and (meta)heuristic methods. In recent decades, various classical optimization methods, such as: the λ - γ iterative method, the gradient method, dynamic programming, Lagrangian relaxation, Benders' decomposition based methods, interior-point methods, etc. [1]-[4], have been applied to solve HTC problem. However, most classical methods encounter difficulties in solving highly nonlinear models of extended ED problems, with non-differentiable and non-convex functions, often failing to provide a global optimum and converging to a local optimal solution. Metaheuristic optimization methods are capable of overcoming these shortcomings and addressing the mentioned difficulties. In [4] and [5], the detailed application of metaheuristic optimization methods to solve HTC problems is discussed.

This paper uses the publicly available software package GAMS (General Algebraic Modeling System) to solve the HTC problem. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: after the mathematical models of HPPs and TPPs in Section 2, an optimization model for HTC is proposed in Section 3, while Section 4 applies this model to solve a specific optimization problem in GAMS environment and provides some general remarks on the HTC problem based on the calculation results. The paper is concluded in Section 5.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELS OF POWER PLANTS IN ED PROBLEM

In the mathematical modelling of TPPs for solving an ED problem, each thermal unit is assigned a cost function based on fuel costs, which is generally approximated by a convex quadratic curve [2]:

$$C_n(P_{T_n}) = a_n P_{T_n}^2 + b_n P_{T_n} + c_n \left[\frac{\text{MU}}{\text{h}} \right], \quad (1)$$

where: MU denotes monetary units; a_n [MU/(MW)²h], b_n [MU/MWh] and c_n [MU/h] are the fuel cost coefficients of the thermal unit n ; P_{T_n} [MW] is the power generation of unit n ; and N_T is the number of thermal units. In the presented cost function of TPPs, the operations and maintenance costs are neglected, i.e. the assumption is made that hourly fuel costs are equal to operating costs.

For each generation unit, n , the admissible operating range is taken into consideration, which imposes maximum, $P_{T_n}^{max}$, and minimum output power, $P_{T_n}^{min}$, limits:

$$P_{T_n}^{min} \leq P_{T_n} \leq P_{T_n}^{max}, \quad (2)$$

over the entire optimization period.

In addition to the operational constraints of the units, electricity generation in HPPs is also influenced by hydrological conditions, i.e., the amount of water available for power generation in the HPPs. The dependence on hydrology, as a stochastic parameter, significantly affects long-term and medium-term HTC, whereas in short-term HTC problems, as demonstrated in this study, the uncertainty of hydrology is mitigated, and the amount of available water can be well predicted.

HPPs are mathematically modeled by input-output characteristics [1], which generally describe the correlation between the water discharge rate through turbine, Q_t [m^3/h], power generation, P_H [MW], and hydraulic net head, H_n [m]:

$$Q_t = f(P_H, H_n). \quad (3)$$

Changes in hydraulic head can significantly impact the power output of low-head HPPs. However, for short-term optimization, it is commonly assumed that the net head remains constant during the optimization period.

The optimization procedure typically encompasses impoundment HPPs, and water balance equations are employed to model the changes in reservoir storage volumes within each time interval j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, J$) of the optimization period, T . The water balance equations take into account turbine and spillway releases, natural inflows, and the hydraulic interaction between upstream and downstream units in a coupled system [5]:

$$V_n(j) = V_n(j-1) + t_j \left(Q_{dn}(j) - Q_{tn}(j) - Q_{pn}(j) \right) + \eta t_j \sum_{m \in U_m} (Q_{tm}(j - \tau_m) + Q_{pm}(j - \tau_m)), \quad (4)$$

where following nomenclature is adopted: t_j [h] – duration of a j^{th} time interval; $V_n(j)$ and $V_n(j-1)$ – the reservoir storage volume of n^{th} reservoir at the end of time interval j and $j-1$, respectively, in [m^3]; $Q_{tn}(j)$, $Q_{pn}(j)$ and $Q_{dn}(j)$ – water discharge, spillage and inflow rate of n^{th} HPP, respectively, in [m^3/h], at time interval j ; U_m – number of upstream units directly above n^{th} HPP; $Q_{tm}(j)$ and $Q_{pm}(j)$ – water discharge and spillage of m^{th} unit, in [m^3/h], $m \in U_m$, at j^{th} time interval. The discharge/spillage from any upstream unit, m , is assumed to flow into the succeeding downstream plant with time lag, τ_m . The loss coefficient, η , takes into account the losses of released/spilled water due to evaporation.

Limitations of reservoir storage volumes are defined by:

$$V_n^{\min} \leq V_n(j) \leq V_n^{\max}, \quad (5)$$

where V_n^{\min} and V_n^{\max} are the respective values of minimum and maximum reservoir storage volumes of n^{th} reservoir. Initial and final reservoir storage volumes [5] are denoted as:

$$V_n(j=0) = V_n^{\text{ini}}, \quad (6)$$

$$V_n(j=J) = V_n^{\text{fin}}. \quad (7)$$

The operational constraints of hydropower units that must be adhered to throughout the optimization period include power

and water discharge rate limitations. Output power limitations are defined as:

$$P_{H_n}^{\min} \leq P_{H_n}(j) \leq P_{H_n}^{\max}, \quad (8)$$

where: $P_{H_n}^{\min}$ and $P_{H_n}^{\max}$ are the respective values of minimum and maximum power generation of n^{th} hydropower unit, and $P_{H_n}(j)$ represents its power generation at j^{th} time interval. Limitations of water discharge rate through turbines, at each time interval j , are:

$$Q_{tn}^{\min} \leq Q_{tn}(j) \leq Q_{tn}^{\max}, \quad (9)$$

where: Q_{tn}^{\min} and Q_{tn}^{\max} denote minimum and maximum hourly water discharge rate of n^{th} hydropower unit, respectively.

III. MATHEMATICAL MODEL FOR HTC

In order to model HTC problem, an electric power system with N_H HPPs and N_T TPPs is considered, engaged in supplying load demand of the system, P_D , with transmission losses, P_L . The optimization period is divided into intervals $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$ with a duration of $t_j = T/J$ hours, typically set as $t_j = 1$ h, i.e., temporal discretization of the optimization period is applied.

The objective function, C_T , to be minimized, encompasses the operating costs of all $N_T + N_H$ units, over the entire optimization period, T , [6]:

$$\min C_T =$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^J t_j \left(\zeta \sum_{n=1}^{N_H} P_{H_n}(j) + \sum_{n=1}^{N_T} C_n(P_{T_n}(j)) \right) \text{ [MU]}, \quad (10)$$

where ζ [MU/MW] represents the constant operating costs of HPPs, and $C_n(P_{T_n}(j))$ is a fuel cost function, Eq. (1), of n^{th} TPP, at j^{th} time interval. The hydroelectric power, $P_{H_n}(j)$, is a function of water discharge rate, $Q_{tn}(j)$, and reservoir water head, Eq. (3). This power in turn is a function of reservoir storage volume, $V_n(j)$, [6]:

$$P_{H_n}(j) = c_1^n (V_n(j))^2 + c_2^n (Q_{tn}(j))^2 + c_3^n Q_{tn}(j) V_n(j) + c_4^n V_n(j) + c_5^n Q_{tn}(j) + c_6^n, \quad n = 1, \dots, N_H, \quad (11)$$

where coefficients $c_1^n, c_2^n, \dots, c_6^n$ represent characteristic factors of n^{th} hydropower unit.

The following constraints must be satisfied in each time interval $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$:

- active power balance constraints — the total generation of the engaged units must meet the system load, $P_D(j)$, and also account for transmission losses, $P_L(j)$:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{N_H} P_{H_n}(j) + \sum_{n=1}^{N_T} P_{T_n}(j) = P_D(j) + P_L(j); \quad (12)$$

- water balance equations, Eq. (4);
- operational constraints of hydropower units and reservoirs: Eqs. (5)-(9);

- output power limitations of thermal units, Eq (2);
- ramp-rate limits of thermal units — the operating range of thermal unit is also determined by its dynamic ramp-rate limits. Assuming that the thermal unit currently responds to changes in output power within the defined range, these limits are specified by Eqs. (13) and (14), for increasing and decreasing power generation, respectively:

$$P_{T_n}(j+1) - P_{T_n}(j) \leq RU_n, \quad (13)$$

$$P_{T_n}(j) - P_{T_n}(j+1) \leq RD_n, \quad (14)$$

where RU_n and RD_n denote the upper ramp-rate and down ramp-rate limits. These limits indicate the maximum allowable rate of power increase and decrease for n^{th} thermal unit, when transitioning from the current time interval, j , to the subsequent one, $j+1$. The admissible rate of change of power generation is determined by the thermal stresses of materials and depends on the construction and characteristics of the turbine.

The proposed model could be additionally expanded to include spinning reserve constraints. Also, valve-point loading effects and prohibited operating zones of thermal units, as well as prohibited discharges zones of hydro units could be taken into consideration.

In order to accurately calculate losses, P_L , equations for active and reactive power flows are used with a precise model of the transmission network. However, in real-time active power dispatch, the impact of reactive power flows is often overlooked, resulting in losses being expressed solely as a function of active power generation using B -coefficients, or they may be neglected altogether [1].

IV. CALCULATIONS

The proposed mathematical model was applied to solve the HTC problem of an electric power system with a total of nine HPPs and TPPs, utilizing a publicly available software package GAMS [6], [7]. This package is developed for solving complex optimization problems of large dimensions. It is designed for modelling and solving various types of problems — linear, nonlinear, and mixed integer optimization problems. GAMS is the first algebraic modelling language (AML). Its syntax is inspired by the mathematical notation of optimization models, allowing for concise encoding of optimization problems from various domains. A variety of built-in solvers are available in GAMS for handling different classes of problems. GAMS, like other AMLs, does not solve directly the defined optimization problem, but compiles the source code into the format that embedded solvers can "understand" and solve. This allows for a focus on modelling without getting into the technical details of the solution algorithms. Due to its numerous advantages, GAMS has become a popular tool for both scientific research and solving complex engineering problems.

The considered hydrothermal system comprises five TPPs and multi-chain cascade of four impoundment (reservoir) HPPs, denoted as 1-4, with HPPs 1 and 2 at the same level, HPP 3 downstream from them, and HPP 4 located

downstream from HPP 3. The detailed parameters for the system under consideration are taken from [6], including: the techno-economic characteristics of the power plants, time lags of water flows from upstream reservoirs into the succeeding downstream ones, the loss coefficient, η , as well as the constant operating costs of HPPs, ζ . It must be noted that minor modifications were made to the data provided — the lower limits of the power output of TPP 1 and TPP 2 were set to 125 MW and 165 MW, respectively, while their upper limits were set to 500 MW.

The goal was to determine the optimal load distribution among the committed units to minimize operating costs, while considering operational constraints. The power grid was treated as a black box, meaning that constraints on transmission lines, as well as active and reactive power flows through the branches, are not taken into account. Generation redistribution was performed on an hourly basis, over a 24-hour operating horizon. The hourly water inflows for HPPs and the forecasted hourly load demand of the system were provided in [6].

The proposed HTC model was applied to the units of the considered system, taking into account the provided data, while transmission losses were neglected. The model was implemented in GAMS as a nonlinear programming problem, and GAMS code comprises a total of 505 variables. The embedded solver CONOPT was used for optimization, and the number of iterations was set to 319. The solver took 0.313 s, while the total execution time of the program with displaying results was slightly longer, amounting to 1.297 s. Both mentioned times are relatively short and may vary slightly depending on the performance of the computer where the GAMS software is installed, because the differences in speed among modern computers are generally small.

Fig. 1 depicts the optimal distribution of load among the committed units in TPPs (TPP1-TPP5) and HPPs (HPP1-HPP4), based on the result of the GAMS code execution. Thus, the values of output power for each unit over time, for every hour within 24-hour optimization period, are presented. The total operating costs associated with this optimal generation distribution amount to 661867.641 \$.

Fig. 1. Optimal generation distribution.

For comparison of the efficiency of GAMS in solving HTC problem and the problem of ED of thermal system, the multi-chain cascade of four HPPs in system under consideration is replaced with four TPPs. Two of these TPPs have the same techno-economic characteristics as TPP 1, and the other two have the same characteristics as TPP 2. The mathematical model of economic dispatch of thermal system proposed in [8] was applied to the reconfigured system described in this paper, comprising a total of nine TPPs.

This model was implemented in GAMS as a nonlinear programming problem, and had 217 variables. CONOPT solver was also employed, and needed only 0.031 s to finish calculations, while the total execution time of the program was 1.031 s. The output of the GAMS code was the optimal distribution of load among the committed thermal units, resulting in a total operating costs of 766325.356 \$.

Two main observations based on the conducted calculations could be discussed: the HTC problem is more challenging to solve compared to the problem of optimal generation distribution in a purely thermal system, and the hydrothermal system have lower total operating costs, which indicates that incorporating hydroelectric generation into the system results in significant savings in fuel for the thermal units. The latter observation is attributed to the ability of hydroelectric generation to meet load demand of the system with relatively low operating costs, compared to the thermal units.

Finally, the theoretical cases of load distributions among generating units based solely on their rated powers were analysed. These cases implied the generation distributions proportional to rated powers of the units while all operating constraints except active power balance equations were neglected. It was found that the total operating costs in the hydrothermal system were even lower (649823.380 \$) than the total costs in the hydrothermal system when described HTC model was applied. The total operating costs in a reconfigured, purely thermal system where the generation distributions were proportional to rated powers of the units amounted to 774911.268 \$, and were higher than the costs obtained by economic dispatch of thermal system. However, it should be emphasized that generation distributions based solely on rated powers of the generating units are only hypothetical and would not be sustainable in practical applications.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper deals with hydrothermal coordination problem, that involves the development of adequate mathematical model and the usage of powerful and expensive software. The application of the proposed HTC model is demonstrated in the paper on the example of electric power system. The model is implemented in publicly available software package GAMS as a nonlinear programming problem, and the results of the

execution of GAMS code show that HTC problem can be solved quickly and efficiently in the GAMS environment. It is demonstrated that the problem of economic dispatch of the purely thermal system is solved even more quickly in GAMS environment, and that such kind of power system is characterized by higher operating costs.

Alternative directions for further research into the possibilities and efficiency of applying GAMS software to solve HTC problems include: solving highly nonlinear HTC models with non-smooth and non-convex functions; solving HTC problems that incorporate renewable energy sources; analyzing the application of different solvers to models implemented in GAMS; comparative analysis of the efficiency of GAMS software and (hybrid) metaheuristics in solving complex problems; etc.

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